

JSON FILE STRUCTURE

General parameters - description

Parameter	Description	Value	Example	Related feature in the edCrumble editor
<i>version</i>	Version of the tool when the json file is created. It allows us to import old version json files in new versions of the tool.	Integer.	6	There is no related feature.
<i>designTitle</i>	Title of the design introduced by the user.	Text.	"Mathematics course"	
<i>description</i>	Description of the design introduced by the user.	Text.	"Description of the course..."	

<p><i>evaluation</i></p>	<p>General description of how students will be evaluated within the design, introduced by the user.</p>	<p>Text.</p>	<p>"There is a mid-term exam and a final exam".</p>	
<p><i>experience</i></p>	<p>General description of how was the implementation of the design in class.</p>	<p>Text.</p>	<p>"The design was a success but I would improve..."</p>	

<i>objectivesList</i>	List of learning objectives introduced by the user.	Text list.	["OBJECTIVE 1", "OBJECTIVE 2", "OBJECTIVE 3"]	
<i>students</i>	Number of students expected in the design, introduced by the user.	Text Integer.	"20"	
<i>startDate</i>	Design/course starting date, introduced by the user.	Date.	"2019-11-05T23:00:00.000Z"	
<i>endDate</i>	Design/course ending date, introduced by the user.	Date.	"2019-11-14T22:59:59.000Z"	
<i>topic</i>	Design topic selected from the following list (user selection):	Text Integer. Each topic has an assigned number :	"2"	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Unselected topic</i> 	" "		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>General programmes</i> 	"1"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Education</i> 	"2"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Humanities and arts</i> 	"3"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Social sciences, business and law</i> 	"4"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Science</i> 	"5"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Engineering, manufacturing and construction</i> 	"6"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Agriculture</i> 	"7"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Health and welfare</i> 	"8"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Services</i> 	"9"		
<i>educationalLevel</i>	Education level of the design, selected from the following list:	Text Integer. Each level has an assigned number :	"4"	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unselected educational level 	" "		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early childhood Education 	"1"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary education 	"2"		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower secondary education • Upper secondary education • Post-secondary non-tertiary education • Short-cycle tertiary education • Bachelor or equivalent • Master or equivalent • Doctoral or equivalent 	<p>"3"</p> <p>"4"</p> <p>"5"</p> <p>"6"</p> <p>"7"</p> <p>"8"</p> <p>"9"</p>		
<p><i>last_resource_id</i></p>	<p>Each resource selected within the design has an id. This field reports the id of the last resource added to the design.</p>	<p>Integer.</p>	<p>1</p>	

<p><i>last_item_id</i></p>	<p>Each item (in-class or out-of-class session) within the design has an id. This field reports the id of the last item created.</p>	<p>Integer.</p>	<p>1</p>	
<p><i>resourcesList</i></p>	<p>List of educational resources used in the design.</p>	<p>List of resources objects. (see next tables for further details)</p>	<pre>{ "1": { "id": "1", "type": "pdf", "title": "", "description": "", "medium_type": "1", "medium_name": "", "target_teacher": false, "target_student": true, "url": "" }, "2": { "id": "2", "type": "video", "title": "", "description": "", "medium_type": "1", "medium_name": "", "target_teacher": false, "target_student": true, "url": "" } }</pre>	

itemsList

List of items (in-class and out-of-class sessions) created in the design.

List of items objects.
(see next tables for further details)

```
[{"id":1,"content":  
:"class1","title":  
class1","start":  
2019-11-06T08:  
00:00.000Z","e  
nd":  
2019-11-06T09:  
00:00.000Z","group":1,"c  
lassName":  
"in","tasks":  
[{"type":  
1,"student_role":  
3,"students_g  
roup":2,"teach  
er_role":3,"gra  
ded":1,"min":  
20,"FC":1,"PBL":  
1,"description":  
,"resources":  
1}],  
"objectives":  
[],  
"visibleFrame  
Template":  
"}]
```


resourcesList - description

Parameter in <i>resourcesList</i>	Description	Value	Example	Related feature in the edCrumble editor	
<i>id</i>	Id of the resource. Each new resource has a unique id.	Integer.	2	There is no related feature.	
<i>type</i>	Resource type:	Text. Each resource has an associated text:	"video"	<p>All of them can be found on the resources panel (left side of the edCrumble editor):</p>	
	FILES	file			"file"
	picture	"picture"			
	video	"video"			
	ppt	"ppt"			
	pdf	"pdf"			
	audio	"audio"			
	spreadsheet	"spreadsheet"			
	code	"code"			
blank	"blank"				

	APPS	edpuzzle	"edpuzzle"	
		pyramid	"pyramid"	
		socrative	"socrative"	
		kahoot	"kahoot"	
		ldfeedback	"ldfeedback"	
		padlet	"padlet"	
		googleforms	"googleforms"	
		googlemaps	"googlemaps"	
		plickers	"plickers"	
		eduloc	"eduloc"	
		quizlet	"quizlet"	
		symbaloo	"symbaloo"	
		lessonPlan	"lessonPlan"	
blankApp	"blankApp"			

	PHYSICAL	book	"book"		
		electronics	"electronics"		
		laboratory	"laboratory"		
		medical	"medical"		
		mechanics	"mechanics"		
		crafts	"crafts"		
		painting	"painting"		
		sports	"sports"		
		games	"games"		
		nature	"nature"		
		cooking	"cooking"		
		food	"food"		
		audioEquipment	"audioEquipment"		
		videoEquipment	"videoEquipment"		
		physicalartifact	"physicalartifact"		

	COMMUNIC	email	"email"	<p>The image shows two screenshots of a mobile application interface. The top screenshot displays a menu with categories: Files, Apps, Physical, Communi, Social, and MOOCs. Under the 'Communi' category, there are icons for Email (@), Forum (speech bubble), Slack (#), and WhatsApp (phone handset). Under the 'Social' category, there are icons for Skype (S), Google Hangouts (G), and Other Communic. The bottom screenshot shows the same menu with 'Communi' highlighted. Under 'Communi', there are icons for Facebook (f), Twitter (bird), LinkedIn (in), and Instagram (camera). Under 'Social', there are icons for Snapchat (ghost), Pinterest (P), Google Plus (G+), and Other Social (star).</p>
		forum	"forum"	
		slack	"slack"	
		whatsapp	"whatsapp"	
		skype	"skype"	
		hangouts	"hangouts"	
		othercommunic	"othercommunic"	
	SOCIAL	facebook	"facebook"	
		twitter	"twitter"	
		linkedin	"linkedin"	
		instagram	"instagram"	
		snapchat	"snapchat"	
		pinterest	"pinterest"	
		googleplus	"googleplus"	
othersocial	"othersocial"			

<p><i>title</i></p>	<p>Title of the resource introduced by the user (optional field).</p>	<p>Text.</p>	<p>"Book1"</p>	
<p><i>description</i></p>	<p>Description of the resource introduced by the user (optional field).</p>	<p>Text.</p>	<p>"Book for covering the concepts of the lesson 1"</p>	
<p><i>medium_type</i></p>	<p>Medium type where a resource will be hosted (from which the resource will be delivered to the students). User can select the medium from the following list:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Miscelania ● LMS (Learning Management System) ● Local Storage ● MOOC platform (Coursera, edx, MiriadaX, FutureLearn...) 	<p>Integer text. Each medium has an associated number:</p>	<p>"3"</p>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web 	"5"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical artifact 	"6"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud storage 	"7"		
<i>medium_name</i>	Name introduced by the user related to the medium selected (optional).	Text.	"Moodle of the School"	
<i>target_teacher</i>	Check box that can be checked by the user to indicate that the resource is for the teachers of the course.	Boolean (false or true).	false	
<i>target_student</i>	Check box that can be checked by the user to indicate that the resource is for the students.	Boolean (false or true).	true	

<i>url</i>	URL of a resource (optional).	Text.	"https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X1DtcZ_qH7Q"	
<i>content</i>	Resource uploaded to edCrumble (optional). It contains the following fields:	Object		
	● <i>data</i>	Text.	"..."	
	● <i>filename</i>	Text.	"Name of the file"	
	● <i>filetype</i>	Text.	"application/pdf"	
	● <i>size</i>	Integer	108733	

itemsList - description

Note: an item in edCrumble is a session placed in the timeline. It can be placed in one of the two timeline layers: in-class or out-of-class layers.

Parameter in <i>itemsList</i>	Description	Value	Example	Related feature in the edCrumble editor
<i>id</i>	Item id (each item has a unique id).	Integer.	1	There is no related feature.

<i>content</i>	Title that user introduce when creating the item.	Text.	"Class 1"	
<i>title</i>	Title that user introduce when creating the item.	Text.	"Class 1"	
<i>start</i>	Date and time when the item starts in the timeline.	Date and time.	"2019-11-06 T08:00:00.0 00Z"	
<i>end</i>	Date and time when the item ends in the timeline.	Date and time.	"2019-11-06 T08:22:00.0 00Z"	

<i>group</i>	Indicates if the item has been placed in the in-class layer or in the out-class layer.	Integer (1: in-class, 2: out-of-class)	1	There is no related feature.
<i>className</i>	Indicates if the item has been placed in the in-class layer or in the out-class layer.	Text ("in": in-class, "out": out-of-class)	"in"	There is no related feature.
<i>tasks</i>	List of the tasks created within the item.	List of objects (see next table for further details).	<pre>[{"type": "1", "student_role": "1", "students_group": "2", "teacher_role": "1", "graded": "1", "min": "20", "FC": "1", "PBL": "1", "description": "", "resources": [2]}</pre>	

<i>objectives</i>	List of objectives selected by the user within this item. The list of objectives that can be selected is the list introduced in the <i>objectivesList</i> field.	Text list. The length of the list is the same as the length of <i>objectivesList</i> . If one objective is selected there is "1" on each position in the list, otherwise is null.	[null,"1","1"]	
<i>visibleFrame Template</i>		Text.	""	

tasks - description

Note: each item in edCrumble can have a list of tasks. Each task is a part of a in-class or out-of-class sessions. See next picture which shows an item with two tasks.:

Parameter in tasks	Description	Value	Example	Related feature in the edCrumble editor
<i>type</i>	Bloom's taxonomy selected by the user for a specific task. Options:	Integer. Each option has its own value:	3	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neutral 	1		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remembering 	2		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding 	3		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applying 	4		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysing 	5		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluating 	6		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating 	7		
<i>student_role</i>	Student type of work. User can select from the following options:	Text integer. Each option has its own value:	"1"	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual 	"1"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group 	"2"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All class 	"3"		
<i>students_group</i>	Number of students per group.	Text integer. By default is 2. If student_role is "2"	"5"	

		user can change this number.		
<i>teacher_role</i>	Teacher availability in the task. User can select from the following options:	Text integer. Each option has its own value:	"3"	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher is not present 	"1"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher is available online 	"2"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher available f2f 	"3"		
<i>graded</i>	Type of grading. User can select from the following options:		"2"	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not graded 	"1"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Auto evaluation 	"2"		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Graded 	"3"		
<i>min</i>	Duration of the task in minutes.	Text number.	"20"	

<p>FC</p>	<p>Step selected of the Flipped Classroom (FC) guidelines. Options:</p>	<p>Integer. Each step has its own value:</p>	<p>6</p>	<p>The top screenshot shows the 'Guides configuration' window with 'Flipped Classroom (FC)' and 'Problem Based Learning (PBL)' toggle switches. The middle screenshot shows a class interface with a dropdown menu for 'FC' open, listing steps from Pas1 to Pas9. The bottom screenshot shows a similar interface but with a dropdown menu for 'PBL' open, listing steps from Pas1 to Pas7, with a tooltip for 'Pas6'.</p>
<p>PBL</p>	<p>Step selected of the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) guidelines. Options:</p>	<p>Integer. Each step has its own value:</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The top screenshot shows the 'Guides configuration' window with 'Flipped Classroom (FC)' and 'Problem Based Learning (PBL)' toggle switches. The middle screenshot shows a class interface with a dropdown menu for 'PBL' open, listing steps from Pas1 to Pas7, with a tooltip for 'Pas6'.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step4 	5		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step5 	6		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step6 	7		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step7 	8		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ref. 	9		
<i>description</i>	Description of the task introduced by the user.	Text.	"Read the assignment 1"	
<i>resources</i>	List of id's of the resources used within the task.	List of integers (id's of the resources).	[3,4]	